

A COMPARATIVE INVESTIGATION OF MORPHOLOGICAL PROCESSES IN HAUSA AND JAAKU LANGUAGES

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20507066>

<p>Keywords: Comparative Linguistics, Word Formation, Derivation, Compounding, Hausa and Labur</p>	<p>Abstract: <i>Comparative linguistic studies help to identify similarities and differences among languages and enhance the understanding of their structures. This study examines word formation processes in Hausa and Labur (Jaku) languages, focusing on derivation and compounding. Hausa is a Chadic language of the Afro-Asiatic family, while Labur is a Bantoid language spoken in Bauchi State, Nigeria. Using a comparative approach, the study investigates how new words are formed in both languages through derivational and compounding processes. The findings reveal that both languages utilize derivation and compounding as productive means of word formation, despite belonging to different language families. However, differences are observed in their morphological patterns, affixation processes, and compound word structures. The study concludes that Hausa and Labur share certain similarities in word formation while maintaining distinctive linguistic features. The research contributes to comparative morphology and provides further insight into the structural characteristics of indigenous Nigerian languages.</i></p>
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Introduction

The process of demonstrating and bringing to light the discrepancies and possible similarities in a given linguistic process or phenomenon is carried out through comparative study between languages (Suleyman 2010). The study of how languages are differently structured began out of the interest to classify language families across the world. This was initiated by comparative linguists whose efforts were geared towards demonstrating similarities. However,

comparative studies have shown that languages may share resemblances without being genetically related (Buhari, 2011).

Hausa is a Chadic language, a branch of the Afro-Asiatic language family widely spoken as a first language in the Northern part of Nigeria and Southern Niger Republic (Furniss, 1996 and Adam, 1997). On the other hand, Labur (Jaku) is a Bantoid language of the Southern Jarawan Bantu languages of Nigeria spoken in Bauchi State (Lewis, et al 2015).

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In this regard, this paper therefore, seeks to examine the areas of similarities and differences between two unrelated languages (Hausa and Labur) in relation to word formation processes through derivation and compounding.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Despite the long distance between families of the two languages, there exist some similarities pertaining to the derivation and compounding. Most of the present Labur speakers are bilingual with Hausa as their second language which yielded some impact on the use of their mother tongue. This was what triggered the researcher to carry out a comparative study particularly on derivation and compounding in the two languages with the aim of finding out areas of differences and congruence in these two morphological processes. These two processes were chosen simply because they all deal with word formation.

Base Form	Patronymic Noun	Gloss
Háúsá	Bàháúshèè	Hausa man
Kánòò	Bàkánèè	Kano man
Jààkú	Bàjààkúú	Jaku man
Jààr	Bàjààrí	Jar man
Gàlàmbí	Bàgàlàmbí	Galambi man

The patronymics in the examples given above indicate class of words referring to individuals as people of the areas to which the base form denotes. The process is done by prefixing a

1.2 Derivational Formation in the Hausa and Labur Languages

Derivation is one of the morphological processes that involve the addition of an affix to a base form (Fagge, 2004). The processes of adding a bound morpheme 'bà' to a base form to indicate patronymics or place of origin of a person referred to and adding of a bound morpheme 'má' to a verb base to indicate an agentive noun, instrumental noun and locative noun in the Hausa language were compared with the processes in the Labur language.

Patronymics are a class of words referring to individuals as a people of the areas to which the base form denotes (Abubakar, 2001). The base is either a place or a language name. The examples of patronymics in Hausa are as follows:

bound morpheme "bà-" to the base form and the derived form takes a final vowel "-èè" as is the first two examples, final vowel "-úú" as in the third example and final vowel "-íí" as in the last

two examples above. This is in the case of a masculine form of the words. The feminine form is derived from its corresponding masculine form. Therefore, in the case of the examples above, masculine forms that has final vowel “-èè”, the feminine form takes “-iyáá” as in “Bàháúshèè – Bàháúshiyáá”. The masculine form that ends with vowel “-úú” takes “úwáá” as the final vowel of the feminine form as in “Bàjààkúú – Bàjààkúwáá”. And the masculine form that ends with vowel “-íí” takes

Verb	Gloss	Agentive Noun	Gloss
xínkàà	sew	máxìnkíí	Tailor
bùgàà	beat	mábùgíí	beater
háwáá	ride	máhàýíí	rider
sánìì	know	másàníí	knowledgeable person
nóómàà	till	mánòòmíí	farmer

The examples above clearly depict that in Hausa, agentive nouns are derived by prefixing a bound morpheme “má-” to a verb base. The final vowel of the masculine form is “-íí”. The feminine form that is derived from the masculine form takes “-iyáá” as its final vowel as in “máxìnkíí – máxìnkìiyáá”. The tone of the masculine form is high-low-high (HLH) and for the feminine form is high-high- low-high (HHLH). The vowel “-áá” is suffix to the

Verb	Gloss	Locative Noun	Literal Meaning	Free Meaning
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the vowel “-áá” in the feminine form as in “Bàjààríí – Bàjààráá”. The plural form of patronymics is form by suffixing “-àwáá” to the base form without the prefix “bà-” as in “Háúsá – Hàùsààwáá”.

1.2.2 Agentive Noun in the Hausa Language

In deriving agentive noun in the Hausa language a bound morpheme “má-” is prefixed (Abubakar, 2001), as in the following examples;

agentive noun to indicate its plural form as in “máxìnkíí – máxìnkáá”

1.2.3 Locative Noun in the Labur Language

To form a locative nouns in the Labur language, one has to add a free morpheme ‘bàn’ (which means a place) to a verb. In some instances, the word ‘gìr’(a thing) follows the verb as in the examples below;

nwààni	drink	bàn nwààni	place of drinking	a drinking place
Sórúm	hide	bàn sórúm	place of hiding	a hiding place
Hìrxì	join	bàn hìrxì	place of meeting	a meeting place
lààmni	cook	bàn lààmni gír	place of cooking a thing	a kitchen
tùlli	slaughter	bàn tùllin gír	place of smithing a thing	a smithy

1.3 Noun-based Compounds in Hausa

Noun-based compounds are those that the nucleus or base of the compound word is a noun.

For examples;

Compound	Literal Meaning	Free Meaning
úwár-gídáá	mother of house	senior wife
`yán-fáshì	sons of robbing	armed robbers
láyàr-záánáá	charm of weaved gamba grass	amulet
vàráúniyár-hányàà	thief of way	a short cut way
bàkán-gízòò	bow of spider	rainbow

Examples of noun-based compounds above comprises of two nouns joined by a genitival linker -n/-

r. Therefore, this category has the structure ‘Noun + Genitive Link + Noun’ as in “úwáá + r + gídáá – úwár-gídáá” as in the examples above.

Compound	Literal Meaning	Free Meaning
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1.3.1 Noun-based Compounds in Labur

Like in the Hausa language, compounds that have a noun as its nucleus or base in the Labur language are referred to as noun-based compounds. For examples;

gwààl-gùn	bark of tree	a paper
màn-ngìvìí	man of stealing	a thief
fùsù-gwál	horse of millipede	a bicycle
gùn-mèl	tree of neck	a wrist
ngìv-jár	thieve of way	a short cut way

From the examples above, it appears that in the Labur language two nouns are joined together to form compound nouns. However, the nouns are not necessarily linked with a genitive link ‘-n/-r’ as is commonly found in the Hausa language. Therefore, it is a ‘Noun + Noun’ compound formation as in “gwààl + gùn - gwààl- gùn”.

Compound	Literal Meaning
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hàrà-qáryáá	preventing lying
dàkí-bàríí	beat and leave it
hàrà-rántsúwáá	prevent oath
bùgùn-shááhòò	beating of hawk
dákàn-mázáá	pounding of men

The examples of verb-based compounds above has the structure of ‘Verb + Noun’ as in “hàràqáryáá”. However, in some instances a genitive link ‘-n/-r’ is used to join the two words in the compound as in “bùgùn + n + shááhòò – bùgùn-shááhòò” examples;

1.3.2 Verb-based Compounds in Hausa

In Hausa there are compounds that are referred to as verb-based compounds. This is because they have a verb as a core as in the following examples;

Free Meaning
hair under lower lip
strong/reliable thing
an exception mentally ill person
type of herb

1.3.3 Verb-based Compounds in Labur

Verb-based compounds are also found in the Labur language as in the following

Compound	Literal Meaning	Free Meaning
nyálín jār	blocking the road	armed robbery
hìrxìn múxùù	joining head	unity
wà'àn múxùù	hearing of head	courtesy visit
zùvùn mìshìì	closing of eye	trick
hìrxìn kún	joining of mouth	conspiracy

Verb-based compound construction in Labur has the structure of 'Verb + Genitive link + Noun' as in 'nyálíí + n + jār'.

1.3.4 Numerical-based Compounds in Hausa

In the Hausa language, numerical-based compounds are produced by either partial

Compound	Literal Meaning	Free Meaning
xáxxáyáá	one-one	one each
bíbbíyúú	two-two	two each
úkù-úkùù	three-three	three each
shàà-úkùù	drink three	thirteen
shàà -húxúú	drink four	fourteen

From the examples above, numerical-based compounding through partial Reduplication can be seen as in "xáxxáyáá" and "bíbbíyúú" . Example of complete reduplication

Compound	Literal Meaning	Free Meaning
		is the structure "úkù-úkùù" where the complete stem is repeated. And examples indicating a 'Verb + Noun' numerical compound formation is as in "shàà-úkùù" and" shàà-húxúú".

mù mòk	one-one	one each
vúváár	two-two	two each
títáád	three-three	three each
lùm kwáán mò'óó	ten fell one	eleven
lùm kwáán váár	ten fell two	twelve

In Labur language, partial reduplication in the formation of numerical-based compound is found as in the first three examples above. However, the construction of the last two examples is of a 'Noun + Verb + Noun' as in "lùm + kwáán + mò'óó - lùm-kwáán-mò'óó".

1.4 Conclusion

Based on the discussion presented above, it is clear that there are some areas of similarities as well as differences between the derivational and compounding processes in the Hausa and Labur languages. From the data analysed, the Hausa

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language form words through derivation and compound processes. As regard to the process of derivation, Hausa prefix a bound morpheme 'bà' to a noun base to derive patronymics, and prefix a bound morpheme 'ma' to a verb base to derive agentive, instrumental and locative nouns. But in the case of Labur language, patronymics are formed either through coinage or apocoptation. Concerning the formation of agentive, instrumental and locative nouns, the process is through prefixing some free morphemes to a verb.

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